
THE EFFECT OF DISTRIBUTION STRENGTH ON CUSTOMER SATISFACTION IN PT SEMEN TIGA RODA

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Abstract:

Distribution is an activity that must be carried out by every company in order to cause and guarantee the supply of products in the market so that people get, then in an effort to find and obtain products that are expected to fulfill some of their life needs. The purpose of this study was to determine how much influence the smooth distribution with customer satisfaction at PT Semen Tiga Roda. Distribution channels are a device that is interdependent in providing a product or service to be used or consumed by consumers or business users. Satisfaction is the feeling of being happy or disappointed someone who appears after comparing the performance (results) of the product that is thought of the expected performance. The population studied was 50 respondents and a sample of 20 respondents was taken with random sampling. The research method used is the library method and field method by means of questionnaire spread. The type of data used by the author is qualitative data originating from the questionnaire which then answers the respondents given a score so that it becomes quantitative data. From the results of these calculations obtained hypothesis test results, namely: $Y = 18.28 + 0.43 X$, $r = 0.56$, and $t = 2.866$. From the results of statistical calculations have obtained a correlation coefficient of 0.56, which means that the smooth distribution with customer satisfaction has a positive and very significant influence, while the coefficient of determination obtained at 31.36% turned out to be influenced by the smooth distribution of the good, the rest of 68.64% is influenced by other factors (returns, after-sales and services) that are not examined directly by the author. In the research hypothesis test also obtained the value of t count 2.866 greater than t table 2.101, with an error rate of 5% (0.05) then according to the applicable provisions means that H_a is accepted and H_0 is rejected.

Keywords: Smooth Distribution; Customer Satisfaction.

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1. Introduction

To support marketing success which will ultimately have an impact on the success of sales activities, this will depend on the ability of sales management, so this will depend on the ability of management to analyze and utilize various variables and strategically design marketing programs within the framework the environment faced by the company and the ease of the plan.

Distribution is one variable from several other marketing variables so that it is very important to be considered by every company. Determination of distribution channels as one of the critical activities faced by management because it can affect all other marketing decisions. In addition, the selection of distribution channels will involve decisions regarding the use of distributors or marketing intermediaries such as wholesalers, agents, brokers, retailers, and other types of suppliers and how to establish good and mutually beneficial relationships with these intermediaries or distributors in the long term.

Using intermediaries means releasing some power over how and to whom the product will be sold. The existence of limited resources, extensive market area coverage, level of competition and other considerations are some reasons for most producers to surrender a certain amount of sales assignments to intermediaries.

Good and timely distribution will help a company to retain its customers because with good distribution, customers will be satisfied and will be loyal to the company so that the company will survive and exist in business activities.

2. Literature Review

Definition of Distribution Channels

The distribution channel is a marketing intermediary path both in the transportation and storage of a product of goods and services from the hands of producers to the consumers. Among the producers and consumers there are marketing intermediaries, namely wholesalers (distributors / agents) who serve buyers of retailers (retailers) and retailers (retailers) who dilute products to the final consumer.

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According to David A Revzan the distribution channel is a path through which the flow of goods from producers to intermediaries and finally to the hands of consumers / users.

Smoothness that comes from the word fluent, where the meaning of fluency in the large dictionary of Indonesian is not stuck, uninterrupted or not halting. Whereas the fluency itself means that something is said in a smooth state. While distribution is a marketing intermediary path both transportation and storage of a product of goods and services from the hands of producers into the hands of consumers.

2.1. Distribution Strategy Techniques.

To get greater profits, the right distribution strategy is needed to distribute goods or services to consumers. The following are the distribution methods that can be chosen by a business company to maximize profits.

2.2. Types / Types of Distribution Channels

1) Manufacturers - Consumers.

That is a form of the shortest distribution channel and the simplest is a distribution channel from producers to consumers, without using intermediaries. Example: Workshop, Restaurant, Barbershop, Salon, Massage parlor and others.

2) Manufacturers - Retailers - Consumers

This distribution channel is also referred to as a direct distribution channel because here large retailers directly make purchases to producers. Example: Newspaper, Ice Cream, and others.

3) Manufacturers - Wholesalers - Retailers - Consumers.

This kind of distribution channel is widely used by producers and is called a traditional distribution channel. Here manufacturers only serve large amounts of sales, not selling to retailers. Purchases by retailers are served by wholesalers, and purchases by consumers are only served by retailers. Example: Instant noodles, rice, vegetables, bottled drinks and more.

4) Manufacturers - Agents - Retailers - Consumers.

In this distribution channel producers choose agents as suppliers. Producers carry out large trading activities, in existing distribution channels. The sales target is mainly aimed at large retailers. Example: Imported Goods.

5) Producers - Agents - Wholesalers - Retailers - Consumers.

In distribution channels, often using agents as intermediaries to distribute goods to large traders who then sell to small shops where the small shops distribute directly to consumers.

Definition of Customer Satisfaction

Satisfaction is the feeling of being happy or disappointed someone who appears after comparing the performance (results) of the product that is thought to the expected performance (results) (Kotler Philip, 2009: 177). Customer satisfaction is a situation where the customer's desires,

expectations, and needs are met. A service is considered satisfactory if the service can meet customer needs and expectations.

Customer satisfaction measurement is an important element in providing better, more efficient and more effective services. If the customer feels dissatisfied with a service provided, then the service can be ascertained ineffective and inefficient.

2.3. Customer Satisfaction Strategy

The customer or consumer satisfaction strategy basically is a way that can be done by a company that aims to make the company superior to competing companies

As for some strategies that can be done to reach and increase customer satisfaction:

1) Marketing strategy in the form of relation marketing

That is a strategy where exchange transactions between seller and buyer are continuous, do not stop or end after the sale is completed. In other words the company establishes partnerships with consumers or customers continuously so as to create consumer loyalty.

2) Superior customer product strategy

Is a form of marketing strategy by offering a product that is better than competing products. Usually the products produced from this strategy have relatively high prices and have better quality.

3) Unconditional Guarantees or Extra Ordinary Guarantes Strategy.

Is a technique that basically has the commitment to give satisfaction to its customers.

Warranty or guarantee is designed to reduce the risk or loss for consumers before and after the purchase of an item.

4) Efficient complaint handling strategy.

This strategy is carried out by starting from identifying and determining the source of the problem that causes consumers to feel dissatisfied and complaining. The aspects of handling complaints are: 1. empathy for angry customers, 2. Speed in handling complaints, 3. Fairness or fairness in solving problems, 4. Ease for consumers to contact the company.

2.4. Customer Satisfaction Benefits for companies

The level of customer satisfaction with service is an important factor in developing a service delivery system that is responsive to customer needs, minimizes costs and time and maximizes the impact of service on the target population.

The benefits are: 1. The occurrence of long-term mutually beneficial relations between the company and its customers, 2. The opening of opportunities for business growth through repeat purchases, 3. Customer loyalty can be formed, 4. The occurrence of positive mouth-to-mouth communication attract new customers, 5. Customer and public perceptions of the company's reputation are increasingly positive. 6. Profits earned can increase.

3. Research Methodology

The location of the research questionnaire is in the material stores in the Klender District, and East Jakarta Duren Palm Subdistricts as many as 20 stores randomly, within 2 months in November

and December 2018. The research method used is the field research by holding observation and distribution of questionnaires to material shops in the East Jakarta Klender and Duren palm region, and a free library using library data. Adapaun data are qualitative data, data collection techniques by looking for library data and questionnaires, data processing techniques, namely by changing the qualitative data from the results of questionnaire answers filled in by material owners and given weights using the Likert scale into quantitative data. And finally analyzed using a simple linear regression test, correlation, test the coefficient of determination and hypothesis testing.

4. Research Results

To find out whether there is an influence between the smooth distribution and customer satisfaction at PT. Three Wheel Cement, can be known by

using a simple linear regression analysis method, where the symbol of the correlation size is r which ranges from -1 to 1 whose results are as follows: $\sum X = 573$, $\sum Y = 609$, $\sum X^2 = 17,231$, $\sum Y^2 = 19,023$, $\sum XY = 17,800$ and $n = 20$, obtained are $b = 0.43$ and $a = 18.23$, then $Y = 18.23 + 0.43 X$,

meaning that each change in the independent variable X by 1 unit will be offset by the existence of a dependent change of Y of 18.23 units, with the addition of 1 element of the smooth distribution means that the increase in customer satisfaction will increase by 18.23 times. From the correlation test obtained for $r = 0.56$, which means that the smooth distribution with customer satisfaction has a positive and very significant effect, while the value of the coefficient of determination is 31.36%, this means that the smooth distribution affects customer satisfaction at PT Semen Tiga Roda by 31.36%, apparently influenced by the smooth distribution of good, the rest of 68.64% is influenced by other factors not examined directly by the researcher. In the research hypothesis test obtained t count of $2.866 > t$ table 2.101, with an error rate of 5% (0.05), then according to the applicable provisions means that H_a is accepted and H_0 is rejected, which means there is an influence of smooth distribution on customer satisfy

5. Conclusion and Advice

5.1. Conclusion

Based on the results of the research the conclusions are:

- 1) From the linear regression test the results are $b = 0.43$ and $a = 18.23$, then $Y = 18.23 + 0.43X$ means that each change in variable X by 1 unit will be offset by the existence of a dependent change of Y of 18.23 unit.
- 2) From the correlation test obtained $r = 0.56$ which means that between the smooth distribution and satisfaction there is a positive and significant influence. From the coefficient of determination test obtained $Kd = 31.36\%$ it turns out that the smooth distribution affects customer satisfaction by 31.36% and 68.64% is influenced by other factors not examined directly by the researcher
- 3) From the hypothesis test, the calculation is $2.866 > t$ table 2.101 with an error rate of 5% (0.05) then H_a is accepted and H_0 is rejected, which means that there is an influence on the smooth distribution of customer satisfaction at PT Semen Tiga Roda

5.2. Suggestion

Based on the conclusions, the suggestions are:

- 1) To be able to achieve maximum service, the management of the PT. Semen Tiga Roda Department company can implement a better distribution system so that customers can increase again.
- 2) The management of the company should give more serious attention to the distribution system because this is very important in increasing customer satisfaction so that the cement supply in the material remains smooth.
- 3) There is openness between the management of the company and the customers so that every time there is a company problem, it can be addressed together and a solution is sought.
- 4) The existence of good cooperation between the cement factory and the distributor, transportation services so that the creation of synergies for the smooth distribution of cement to the material.

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